

Thermodynamic Molar Properties of Aqueous Solutions of Ca and Mg Salts using Sound Velocity Measurements

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The partial molar volumes and compressibilities of Mg acetate, Mg chloride, MgSO₄, Ca acetate, Ca chloride and CaSO₄ solutions at 25°, are calculated from densities and sound velocity measurements in the concentration range 0.005 and 1.0M.

The values of partial molar volumes at infinite dilution were also obtained from ϕ_v vs C plots. Their values were found to decrease in the order Mg acetate > Mg chloride > MgSO₄ for Mg salts and Ca acetate > Ca chloride > CaSO₄ for Ca salts.

The apparent molar compressibilities at infinite dilution were obtained using two methods and were found to follow the trend Ca acetate > CaCl₂ > CaSO₄ for Ca salts and MgCl₂ > Mg acetate > MgSO₄ for Mg salts.

THE information concerning the apparent and partial molar volume is very useful for studying structural interaction in associated and non-associated electrolytes. Several strong electrolytes in very dilute solutions were studied by Lamb and Lee¹. Masson and Dunn² calculated the apparent molar volumes (ϕ_v 's) as a function of molar concentration (C) according to the relation

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^\circ + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (1)$$

where ϕ_v° and S_v are the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and the experimental slope respectively. S_v varies with each electrolyte. The ϕ_v° and S_v values for several electrolytes³⁻¹⁰ have been determined using eq. (1) in water.

In this communication partial molar volumes and compressibilities of CaCl₂, CaSO₄, Ca(OAc)₂, MgCl₂, MgSO₄ and Mg(OAc)₂ are investigated under a wide range of concentrations at 25° and one atmospheric pressure. The concentrations varied from 0.005M to 1.0M, which has helped in obtaining the apparent molar volume and compressibilities at infinite dilution.

Experimental

A. Apparatus :

Density measurements were made with 5 ml pycnometer which was calibrated using deionized distilled water.

$$(d_{4}^{25} = 0.99707 \text{ gm} - \text{cm}^{-3} \text{ at } 25^\circ),$$

Sound velocity measurements were done using the sound velocimeter NUS 6100 in junction with a

Beckman counter. 100 ml of sample was introduced into a thermostated water bath for 30 minutes before reading. This time was necessary for temperature equilibrium.

This type of velocimeter has two transducers positioned in a probe that is immersed in the solution to be measured. A pulse is transmitted through the solution by one transducer which triggers, the second transducer to send another pulse and so on. The measured quantity is the pulse repetition frequency F that is determined by (L/U) , where L is the effective length of the bath between the transducers. It is determined also by τ , the total electronic delay time.

Knowing both values U, sound velocity, can be obtained according to eq. (2)

$$F = \frac{L}{U} + \tau \quad \dots (2)$$

The frequency readings were detected by the counter and automatically recorded on a printer assembled with the velocimeter. The temperature of the water bath was maintained constant at $25 \pm 0.01^\circ$ during the density measurements. However a Leeds Northop oil bath maintained the temperature at $25 \pm 0.002^\circ$ for measuring the sound velocity.

B. Chemicals :

Mg and Ca salts were Fisher reagents grade. It was recrystallized from deionized distilled water and dried before use. Stock solutions of the reagents were prepared and exact concentrations of the stock solutions were checked using edta titration

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and ion-exchange resin techniques. Further dilutions were made just before running the experiments.

Results and Discussion

The apparent molar volumes of the salts at different concentrations are calculated according to eq. (3)

$$\phi_V = \frac{M}{d} - \frac{1000(d - d_0)}{d_0 c} \quad \dots (3)$$

where M is the molecular weight for each salt, d_0 is the density of the solvent (water in this case) and d is the density of the electrolyte at each concentration. The ϕ_V values for $MgCl_2$ and $CaCl_2$ are in good agreement with those of Dun¹⁰ (within the limited concentration used). Our results, however, are made using a much wider concentration range. From the plot of ϕ_V against \sqrt{C} the apparent molar volume at infinite dilution, ϕ_V^0 , can be determined from the extrapolation to the zero concentration.

The precise measurements of the sound velocities of the above salts at various concentrations allow the calculation of apparent molar compressibilities at each concentration as well as at infinite dilution. The sound velocity of the solution U at concentration C and for pure water U_0 are obtained experimentally, and their difference ΔU is plotted against C according to eq. (4)

$$\Delta U = U - U_0 = FC \quad \dots (4)$$

where F is a parameter computed from the curve as shown in Fig. 1, which is a straight line passing through the origin.

Fig. 1. Plotting ΔU against C For Mg salts at 25°.

The adiabatic apparent molar compressibilities at infinite dilution, $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$, were determined using two

different methods. The first method makes use of eq. (5)

$$\phi_{\kappa_s}^0 = \beta_{os} \left\{ 2\phi_V^0 - \left[\frac{M}{d_0} \right] - \left[\frac{200 F}{U_0} \right] \right\} \quad \dots (5)$$

where β_{os} is the compressibility of pure solvent, water in this case = 2.4754×10^{-11} .

The $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$ and the F values for the electrolytes under investigation are listed in Table 7. The $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$ values are also obtained utilizing equations (6), (7) and (8) and plotting ϕ_{κ_s} against \sqrt{C} .

$$\beta_s = \frac{1}{U^2 d} \quad \dots (6)$$

$$\phi_{\kappa_s} = \frac{1000(\beta_s d_0 - \beta_{os} d)}{C d_0} + \frac{M \beta_s}{d} \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\phi_{\kappa_s} = \phi_{\kappa_s}^0 + S_{\kappa_s} \sqrt{C} \quad \dots (8)$$

Extrapolation of the linear part to the zero concentration will provide $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$. Fig. 2 shows these plots for Mg salts.

Fig. 2. Plotting apparent molar compressibilities ϕ_{κ_s} against \sqrt{C} for Mg salts at 25°.

In most cases which are reported in the literature on similar systems the two methods yielded different results. The extrapolation procedure always gave lower values for $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$. The reasons may be that the limiting law is not applicable and the small differences in the concentrations for obtaining U and d when not measured at the same time.

It is interesting that the values of $\phi_{\kappa_s}^0$ obtained from the two methods in all our salts, except for $CaSO_4$, are in fairly good agreement with each other, as shown in Table 6 columns 4 and 5. It should be noticed that the concentration range for

TABLE 1—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF MAGNESIUM ACETATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (Mole/L)	Density (g-cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ³ -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.08	1.00012	39.18	1.5008	4.4393	-102.68
0.05	1.0017	50.01	1.5042	4.4122	-105.92
0.10	1.0057	56.33	1.5123	4.3478	-104.80
0.20	1.0135	60.49	1.5277	4.3277	-101.35
0.30	1.0213	61.88	1.5428	4.1137	-99.44
0.40	1.0288	63.32	1.5576	4.0065	-97.52
0.50	1.0362	64.40	1.5723	3.9038	-95.71
0.60	1.0440	64.43	1.5870	3.8033	-95.24
0.70	1.0507	66.04	1.6017	3.7098	-93.65
0.80	1.0580	66.49	1.6160	3.6193	-92.36
0.90	1.0638	68.52	1.6303	3.5371	-90.17
1.00	1.0736	66.13	1.6445	3.4440	-91.71

TABLE 2—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF MAGNESIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (mole/L)	Density (g-cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ³ -mole ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.03	1.0002	8.97	1.4992	4.4432	-95.01
0.05	1.0017	1.612	1.5015	4.4280	-94.21
0.10	1.0055	10.94	1.5071	4.3785	-91.01
0.20	1.0132	15.40	1.5180	4.2831	-91.88
0.30	1.0211	15.15	1.5288	4.1900	-92.01
0.40	1.0297	13.67	1.5395	4.0976	-93.16
0.50	1.0362	16.99	1.5501	4.0164	-90.02
0.60	1.0444	16.37	1.5607	3.9310	-90.36
0.70	1.0509	18.36	1.5713	3.8540	-88.35
0.80	1.0583	18.69	1.5820	3.7754	-85.95
1.00	1.0728	19.50	1.6644	3.3648	-115.10

TABLE 3—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF MAGNESIUM SULPHATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (mole/L)	Density (g-cm ³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ³ -mole ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.0125	0.9987	-1.0001	1.4975	4.4652	-85.80
0.025	1.000	-2.77	1.4992	4.4491	-104.55
0.075	1.0062	-2.03	1.5059	4.3823	-126.63
0.10	1.0091	-0.5315	1.5088	4.3529	-124.59
0.125	1.0122	-0.4163	1.5122	4.3202	-127.19
0.20	1.0209	0.9137	1.5211	4.2333	-124.81
0.30	1.0324	2.4355	1.5331	4.1209	-123.05
0.40	1.0440	2.9203	1.5455	4.0101	-122.82
0.50	1.0552	3.9735	1.5577	3.9054	-121.71
0.60	1.0666	4.4917	1.5702	3.8027	-121.22
0.70	1.0786	3.9019	1.5827	3.6669	-126.86
0.80	1.0887	5.4816	1.5955	3.6082	-119.92
0.90	1.0997	6.3473	1.6084	3.5151	-119.42
1.00	1.1120	5.3858	1.6218	3.4188	-120.27

TABLE 4—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF CALCIUM ACETATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (Mole/L)	Density (g-cm ³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² -dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ³ -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.01	0.99807	60.94	1.4973	4.4692	-94.58
0.02	0.99894	67.43	1.4989	4.4557	-68.97
0.03	0.9998	67.43	1.5003	4.4432	-78.26
0.04	1.0008	70.32	1.5017	4.4304	-84.30
0.05	1.0016	70.32	1.5030	4.4197	-82.72
0.10	1.0062	69.62	1.5094	4.3622	-84.71
0.20	1.0150	71.26	1.5223	4.2515	-84.85
0.30	1.0237	72.11	1.5333	4.1550	-81.65
0.40	1.0332	70.49	1.5450	4.0548	-82.87
0.50	1.0408	73.44	1.5556	3.9704	-

TABLE 5—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF CALCIUM CHLORIDE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (Mole/L)	Density (g-cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² -dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.02	0.999	15.099	1.4979	4.4615	-63.27
0.03	0.9994	33.87	1.4988	4.4542	-66.18
0.04	1.0006	23.57	1.4998	4.4430	-71.32
0.05	1.0016	20.98	1.5008	4.4326	-78.26
0.10	1.0062	20.38	1.5055	4.385	-83.01
0.20	1.0152	20.93	1.5151	4.2911	-85.93
0.30	1.0238	22.47	1.5242	4.2045	-84.70
0.40	1.0327	22.50	1.5333	4.1189	-84.84
0.50	1.0418	22.97	1.5424	4.0364	-84.55

TABLE 6—DENSITY AND PARTIAL MOLAR PROPERTIES OF CALCIUM SULPHATE SOLUTIONS AT 25°

Concentration (Mole/L)	Density (g-cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume ϕ_v (ml-mol ⁻¹)	Sound velocity (u) meter/sec $\times 10^{-3}$	Adiabatic compressibility (B _s) cm ² -dyn ⁻¹ $\times 10^{11}$	Adiabatic apparent molar compressibility ϕ_{k_s} (cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹) $\times 10^4$
0.006	0.9980	-24.65	1.4964	4.4746	-19.20
0.007	0.9981	-20.14	1.4966	4.4728	-46.46
0.008	0.9983	-16.76	1.4967	4.4716	-55.62
0.009	0.9984	-10.80	1.4968	4.4706	-58.38
0.010	0.9985	-6.040	1.4969	4.4696	-60.41
0.011	0.9986	-9.39	1.4970	4.4682	-60.44
0.012	0.9987	1.108	1.4972	4.4670	-69.54
0.013	0.9989	-3.81	1.4972	4.4656	-77.25
0.014	0.9990	-0.912	1.4973	4.4646	-78.23
0.015	0.9992	-8.94	1.4974	4.4628	-89.03

CaSO₄ is much lower than for the rest of the electrolytes under investigation (Fig. 3) due to its low solubility.

The values of d , ϕ_v , U , β_s and ϕ_{k_s} are given in Tables 1-6. F and $\phi_{k_s}^\circ$ values are given in Table 7.

The partial molar volumes at infinite dilutions ϕ_v° were found to decrease in the order Mg acetate >

Fig. 8. Plotting apparent molar compressibilities ϕ_{k_s} against \sqrt{C} for Ca salts at 25°.

TABLE 7—THERMODYNAMIC APPARENT MOLAR PARAMETERS FOR Ca AND Mg SALTS

Electrolyte	ϕ_v° cm ³ -mol ⁻¹	F m sec ⁻¹ lit mol ⁻¹	$10^4 \phi_{k_s}^\circ$ cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ (Calculated procedure)	$10^4 \phi_{k_s}^\circ$ cm ² -mol ⁻¹ -bar ⁻¹ (Extrapolated procedure)
Mg(oAc) ₂	52.2	151.5	-107.8	-107.7
MgCl ₂	14.25	107.5	-94.27	-94.7
MgSO ₄	-7.0	122.5	-137.54	-129.5
Ca(oAc) ₂	69.9	120.0	-81.03	-85.6
CaCl ₂	18.05	90.5	-87.81	-87.5
CaSO ₄	—	100.0	—	—

Mg chloride > Mg sulphate for Mg salts and Ca acetate > Ca chloride > Ca sulphate for Ca salts.

The apparent molar compressibilities at infinite dilution obtained using the two methods were found to follow the trend Ca acetate > Ca chloride > Ca sulphate for Ca salts and Mg chloride > Mg sulphate for Mg salts.

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